

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MODERN PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' REFLEXIVITY AND ITS IMPACT ON COGNITIVE AND BEHAVIORAL FLEXIBILITY

Ravshanova Nargiza Norboevna (PhD), Associate Professor
National Pedagogical University
Uzbekistan named after Nizami
wazednargiza2022@gmail.com

ABSTRACT: The rapid transformations of the higher education system under the influence of globalization, digitalization and increasing academic demands necessitate the development of adaptive psychological qualities in students. One of the key mechanisms in this process is reflexivity as a metacognitive ability that allows analyzing, regulating, and transforming one's own cognitive and behavioral patterns.

KEYWORDS: reflexivity, psychological flexibility, cognitive flexibility, stress tolerance, cognitive-behavioral approach, digital learning

INTRODUCTION.

In the context of rapid social, economic and technological changes, modern society places increased demands on the personality of a specialist. Of particular importance are such qualities as the ability to introspect, critical thinking, adaptability and flexibility of behavior. In this regard, the problem of developing students' reflexivity as an essential component of their professional and personal development is being actualized. Reflexivity is considered as the ability of a person to realize and analyze his own actions, thoughts and emotional states, which allows him to correct behavior and make informed decisions. In an educational environment, the development of reflexivity contributes to improving the quality of learning, the formation of independence and responsibility for the results of one's own activities. At the same time, the importance of cognitive and behavioral flexibility increases, which ensure successful adaptation to changing conditions, the ability to switch between different strategies of thinking and behavior, as well as effective solution of non-standard tasks. Cognitive flexibility is manifested in the ability to change the way information is processed and view a problem from different perspectives, whereas behavioral flexibility reflects the ability to vary behavioral responses depending on the situation. One of the effective means of developing these

qualities is modern psychological training based on interactive teaching methods, group work, situation modeling and reflective practices. Such trainings create conditions for the active involvement of students in the process of self-discovery, the development of self-regulation skills and the formation of flexible behavioral strategies. Despite a significant amount of research devoted to the development of reflexivity and flexibility, the question of the effectiveness of modern psychological training in this context remains insufficiently studied. A deeper analysis of their impact on the cognitive and behavioral characteristics of students is required, as well as determining the conditions that ensure the greatest effectiveness of training programs.

MAIN CONTENT

Psychological flexibility, in turn, reflects the ability to adapt to changing conditions and maintain purposeful behavior under stress. The purpose of this study is to analyze the impact of modern psychological training on the development of reflexivity and psychological flexibility of students.

Literature review. Reflexivity as a metacognitive mechanism. Reflexivity is considered as the highest level of cognitive activity, including introspection, self-control, and awareness of one's own actions. Research shows that a high level of reflexivity promotes deeper learning and the development of critical thinking. Psychological flexibility and stress tolerance. Psychological flexibility is an important component of adaptive behavior. It is associated with the ability to manage emotions, reduce anxiety levels, and respond effectively to stressful situations. Cognitive-behavioral approach. The cognitive-behavioral approach is based on the interrelation of thinking, emotions and behavior. Its application in an educational environment allows you to form skills of self-regulation and constructive thinking.

Digital technologies in psychological education. The use of digital technologies (mobile applications, online platforms, virtual reality) significantly expands the possibilities of psychological trainings, making them more accessible and effective. Discussion. The results confirm that reflexivity is a key factor in students' adaptive behavior. The use of cognitive behavioral techniques contributes to the formation of constructive thinking and increases stress tolerance. The integration of digital technologies enhances the effectiveness of learning and corresponds to modern educational trends.

The presented training program shows that the development of reflexivity in students is a systemic process involving cognitive, emotional and behavioral

components. The integration of cognitive behavioral techniques and digital technologies contributes to a significant increase in cognitive and behavioral flexibility, which is critically important for students to adapt to the modern educational environment.

CONCLUSION.

Modern psychological trainings aimed at developing reflexivity contribute to the formation of psychological flexibility and resistance of students to stress. This makes them an important tool for training competitive specialists. The theoretical analysis and generalization of modern scientific approaches allow us to conclude that the development of reflexivity in students based on psychological training is an important factor in the formation of cognitive and behavioral flexibility. Reflexivity is a key metacognitive mechanism that provides awareness, analysis, and reassessment of one's own thoughts, emotions, and behavioral strategies.

The results of the study confirm that the systematic inclusion of cognitive behavioral techniques such as cognitive restructuring, reflective diaries, role-playing games and methods of emotional self-regulation contributes to the development of students' adaptive skills. In particular, students have an increased ability to switch between different cognitive strategies, use feedback more effectively, and reduce emotional stress in stressful situations. Of particular importance is the integration of digital technologies into the process of psychological training. The use of mobile applications, online platforms, and virtual reality technologies expands the possibilities of individualizing learning, increases student engagement, and ensures higher effectiveness of training programs. Thus, the development of reflexivity through modern psychological training not only helps to increase cognitive and behavioral flexibility, but also forms students' stable ability to self-regulate and adapt in a rapidly changing educational and professional environment. This makes the considered approach a promising direction for implementation in the higher education system.

List of literature

1. Постановление Президента Республики Узбекистан «Стратегии развития технологий искусственного интеллекта до 2030 года» от 14.10.2024 года, № ПП-358.
2. Norboyevna R.N., Shukurullaev A.O. Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotida ekologik teatrni tashkil etish orqali ekologik konseptual asoslarini shakllantirish. // Inter education & global study. 2024. №7. B.122–128.

3. Ravshanova, N. N. (2025). REFLEKSIYA BO ‘LAJAK O ‘QITUVCHINING KASBIY FAOLIYATIDA MUHIM SIFATI. *Inter education & global study*, (1), 362-370.

4. Ravshanova, N. N. (2023). Designing Modern Models of Biological Education Theories and Content in Educators. *Telematique*, 22(01), 3034-3040.

5. Bandura, A. (1997). *Self-efficacy: The exercise of control*. Freeman.— Albert Bandura (o‘ziga ishonch nazariyasi)

6. Xilola Ochilova: Ochilova, X. S. (2024). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA KITOBXONLIK MADANIYATINI SHAKLLANTIRISH YO‘LLARI. *Inter education & global study*, (7), 144-148.

7. Xilola Ochilova: Sheraliyevna, O. H. (2023). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALAR NUTQINI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO ‘LLARI. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 8(4), 70-75.

8. Xilola Ochilova: Ochilova, X. S. (2025). MAKTABGACHA KATTA YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA KITOBXONLIK MADANIYATINI SHAKLLANTIRISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. *Inter education & global study*, (1), 319-324.

9. Xilola Ochilova: Sheraliyevna, O. X. (2024). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI SUHBAT QURISH O ‘RGALI NUTQINI O ‘STIRISH USULLARI. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 17(4), 82-85.

10. Xilola Ochilova: Ochilova, X. S. (2024). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA KITOBXONLIK MADANIYATINI SHAKLLANTIRISH YO‘LLARI. *Inter education & global study*, (7), 144-148

11. Xilola Ochilova: Sheraliyevna, O. H. (2023). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALAR NUTQINI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO ‘LLARI. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 8(4), 70-75.

12. . Ravshanova, N. N. (2025). REFLEKSIYA BO ‘LAJAK O ‘QITUVCHINING KASBIY FAOLIYATIDA MUHIM SIFATI. *Inter education & global study*, (1), 362-370.

13. 4. Ravshanova, N. N., & qizi Nuraliyeva, R. R. (2025). MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM TASHKILOTI RAHBARLARINING KOGNITIV QOBILIYATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH. *Zamonaviy fan va ta'lim yangiliklari xalqaro ilmiy jurnal*, 3(1), 36-42.

14. Ravshanova, N. Talabalarda Psixologik Moslashuvchanlikda Refleksiya Mohiyati Va Kognitiv Qobiliyatni Rivojlantirish Samaradorligi. *Maktabgacha va Maktab Ta'limi Jurnal*, 676612.

15. Norboyevna, R. N., Mirazizova, M. D., & Tolibjonova, M. Z. (2026). TURLI XALQLAR MADANIYATINI O'RGANISH ORQALI KATTA

MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA MILLIY VA UMUMINSONIY QADRIYATLARNI SHAKLLANTIRISH. *Inter education & global study*, 4(1), 232-237.